
SOCIAL MEDIA: A PRACTICAL LIBRARIANSHIP AT DADA PATILHAVIDYALAYA LIBRARY KARJAT

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Abstract:

Social media are computer mediated tools that allows people to create share and exchange information ideas and picture/videos in virtual and networks. Social media is the collective of online communications channels dedicated to community based input, interaction content sharing and collaboration, website and applications dedicated to forums, micro blogging, social networking, social duration, and wikis are among the different types of social media. Library 2.0 incorporates Web 2.0 tools like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WeChat, Google+, Reddit, LinkedIn, QZone, etc.

Keywords: Social Media, Library 2.0, Facebook, YouTube

Introduction:

Technology has emerged as a key component in attaining the goals of libraries. Libraries have always been on the forefront to incorporate the emerging technologies in their set up. With the rise of web 2.0 libraries too shifted to the concept of library2.0. Library 2.0 incorporates Web 2.0 tools, thus facilitating an environment that is user centered and connects various academic communities, eventually advancing towards a crucial organization designed to satisfy user needs and current information cultures (Scott, 2013). Latest in the trend is social media. Libraries are already set in the race to accept this new technology. Smart screens packed with features and social media apps have already reached billions of people across the globe. Social media are Web 2.0 tools that are based on user generated content, that is to say that anyone can publish and access

information, collaborate, or build relationships on a single platform (Jue , Marr & Kassotakis, 2010). Social media communities have emerged recently as open and free communication platforms to support real-time information sharing among members (Cao, Lu, Dong, Tang & Li, 2013).

What is Social Media?

Social media are computer mediated tools that allows people to create share and exchange information ideas and picture/videos in virtual and networks. Social media as defined as “a group of Internet based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content. “Social media is the collective of online communications channels dedicated to community based input, interaction content sharing and collaboration, website

and applications dedicated to forums, micro blogging, social networking, social duration, and wikis are among the different types of social media. Social network sites as web based services that allow individuals to construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, articulate an inventory of other users with whom they share a connection, and view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system (Boyd, 2007).

Definition of Social Media:

The term “**Social Media**” is difficult to define but different experts define social media in a different way. “Bradley & McDonald, 2011; Hanna, Rohm, & Crittenden,2011” have defined that the social media is “any Internet-based or mobile application that operates for the purpose of collaboration, which allows participants to connect, create, comment, view, share, rate, discover, profile and exchange user-generated content”. But in simple word “Social Media is referring to an online platform that allows users to link to each other and contribute and share contents/commentary etc., As a whole Social Media is intended to facilitating, collaboration, sharing and conversation through means of Media via internet”. But

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Mon (2015) explains that the term ‘social media’ envisions a new type of media that is shared and participatory in nature, involving others in the information lifecycle of creation, organization, sharing, finding, and use. Information being the watchword is shared in such media as audio, image, video or a combination of these, also known as multimedia. It is central to the building of the social media community which a user is a part of. Information might not be the only reason for a user’s participation in social media. The digital content seen on social media is also created and shared for eliciting reactions. Social media tools may differ in utility, interface, and application, but each supports collaboration and sharing where everybody and anybody can share anything, anywhere, anytime (Joosten, 2012). Examples include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WeChat, Google+, Reddit, LinkedIn, QZone, etc.

Social Media Platforms:

Sr. No	Name	Year of Launch	Founder
1.	Facebook	4 Feb 2004	Mark Zuckerberg
2	Instagram	2010	1) Mike Krieger 2) Kevin Systrom
3	YouTube	2005	1) Jawed Karim 2) Steve Chen 3) Chad Hurley
4	Whatsapp	2009	1) Brian Acton 2) Jan Koum
5	Twitter	2006	1) Jack Dorsey 2) Evan Williams 3) Noah Glass 4) Biz Stone

6	Snapchat	2011	1) Evan Spiegel 2) Bobby Murphy 3) Reggie Brown
7	Flickr	2004	1) Stewart Butterfield 2) Caterina Fake
8	Wechat	2011	Allen Zhang
9	Linkedin	2003	1) Reid Hoffman 2) Konstantin Guericke 3) Jean-Luc Vaillant 4) Allen Blue 5) Eric Ly
10	Pinterest	2010	Ben Silbermann
11	Telegram	2013	1) Pavel Durov 2) Nikolai
12	Myspace	2003	1) Tom Anderson 2) Chris DeWolfe 3) Jon Hart

Reasons for Using Social Media:

1. To seek opinion on the library and its services for self-evaluation purposes, to encourage debate and to instigate an opportunity to respond to library user feedback;
2. To reach library users in their homes or “**virtual spaces**” as today’s modern online library is no longer solely relying on its physical space as an access point;
3. To publicize events, services, news and presence; To encourage collaboration, for example through collection development and building repositories of collaborative content specific to certain user groups;
4. To increase usage of library collections by promoting new and existing content;
5. To connect with other librarians and keep abreast of industry news;
6. To build a sense of community with both users and also with other institutions and industry contacts.
7. To promote the library services, workshops and the events (to increase the library use)

Need of the Study:

A number of the social media is putting an excellent impact on library services. Social media are using in libraries to deliver information to their potential users. Facebook is that the most engaging social media for library professionals that enable libraries to make webpage to succeed in their targeted audiences. Bamidele, Kafilat and Akeem(2019) social media covers and identifies that needs of the library users that’s why social media is suitable to market library sources and services. Moreover, social media is that the first priority to succeed in the space learners and supply them virtual services to their door step. Jain (2013) social media have different tool like Facebook, twitter, blogs, flicker and YouTube use to plug library sources in addition, twitter, blogs and YouTube are well-known social media which helps libraries to make it convenient use of those to market library services.

Chitumbo (2015) urged social media is best tool to market library services. as noted by Adewoyu and Adebara(2016) WhatsApp and Facebook two noticeable social media help libraries

to supply services. Additionally, social media helps the libraries to form things possible for his or her distance customer and supply them quick services and sources. Nataraju and Mulla(2018) disclosed social media support the librarians to share information their end consumers. Rachman and Putri (2018) Indonesian libraries have adopted social media to market their Library services. The library professionals should adopt the social media and provide up to date and virtual services to the end users.

Review of Literature:

At the international level, studies about social media in libraries have been done a lot by using many kinds of approaches. A research by Lili et al. (2013) identified four factors contributing to the success of Tsinghua university library promotion video project with the title "Falling in Love with the Library". Xie and Stevenson (2014) described social media utilization on ten digital libraries. Results show that social media utilization characteristics are a social media type, update frequency, and interaction with users.

Oh, Ozkaya and LaRose (2014) purported that users who engaged in a certain quality of social media interactivity perceived an enhanced sense of community and life satisfaction. This is clear in the way that heightened communication and collaboration make the social media a rallying point for them. As students and faculty members build communication without barrier the social media practice advances within the framework of the community; it moves from a one dimensional online broadcast platform to a multidimensional socially

connected space that creates value for both the library and library users (Young & Rossman, 2015).

Sujata Santosh (2017) assessed the attitude of library professionals working in the central university libraries of India towards the social media applications and found out that majority of the library professionals were had a strong positive attitude towards thesocial media applications.

Rahman (2010) measured the attitude of library professionals of Bangladesh in context of the certain social economic variables towards the information and communication technology. Investigator found out that competency, work performance and anxiety affect the attitude of library professionals towards the ICT.

Ramzan (2010) assessed the attitude of academic library professionals of Pakistan towards the information and Communication Technology. Investigator found out that significant difference was found in the attitude of library professionals working in the public and private libraries and those who were using the computer at home and those who were not using the computer at home.

Application of Social Media in Dada Patil Mahavidyalaya Library:

Dada Patil Mahavidyalaya's Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Library Blog:

Librarians use blogs to disseminate professional and general information, while libraries often use blogs for announcements. Blog is the website consisting of journal like entries that are arranged in reverse chronologically order. These are distinguished by their frequent, usually short, post, and by the way they reflect their owner's personality.

Access Library Blog:

<https://babankumbhar.blogspot.com/>

Library blog has following WebPages:

**PADMABHUSHAN KARMAVEER
DR. BHAURAO PATIL LIBRARY
KARJAT DIST. AHMEDNAGAR**

[LIBRARY HOME](#)
[OUR LIBRARY](#)
[LIBRARY VISION](#)
[LIBRARY MISSION](#)
[LIBRARY COLLECTION](#)
[LIBRARY COMMITTEE](#)
[JOURNALS](#)
[LIBRARY USERS](#)
[LIBRARY PHOTOGRAPHS](#)
[LIBRARIAN PROFILE](#)

[LIBRARIAN PUBLICATIONS](#)
[LIBRARY SERVICES](#)
[BOOK BANK FACILITY](#)
[NEW ARRIVALS](#)
[LIBRARY PROGRAMMS](#)
[E-RESOURCES](#)
[LIBRARY BUILDING](#)
[DIGITAL LIBRARY](#)
[E-BOOKS](#)
[VIDEO GALLERY](#)
[OPEN ACCESS REPOSITORIES](#)
[LIBRARY STAFF](#)
[CURRENT EVENTS](#)

**Dada Patil Mahavidyalaya's Dr.
Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Library
Facebook Page:**

Facebook is a web-based, interactive network that allows users to share information and thoughts over a wide area. It makes possible a connection to those with shared interests across political, economic and geographic

borders. Using Facebook can be an effective way for academic libraries to connect with their user community. By posting updates on Facebook, libraries can inform their users about the library's program and services.

Access Our Library:
<https://www.facebook.com/libdp>

DPMK Digital Library: Whatsapp Group

WhatsApp is a free cross-platform messaging service. It lets users of iPhone and Android smartphones and Mac and Windows PC call and exchange text,

photo, audio and video messages with others across the globe for free, regardless of the recipient's device.

<https://web.whatsapp.com/>

Conclusion:

Social Media is referring to an online platform that allows users to link to each other and contribute and share contents/commentary etc., As a whole Social Media is intended to facilitating, collaboration, sharing and conversation through means of Media via internet”.

Social media tools may differ in utility, interface, and application, but each supports collaboration and sharing where everybody and anybody can share anything, anywhere, anytime. Using Facebook can be an effective way for academic libraries to connect with their user community. Librarians can use blogs to disseminate professional and general information, while libraries often use blogs for announcements.

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